

Administrator Survey Questionnaire

1. Have you ever recommended an instructor to use a technology (software or cloud service) that was not institutionally purchased or licensed?
2. What tool did you recommend and why?
3. Are you aware of any instructor's request to connect or integrate a tool (not institutionally licensed) into other tools that were institutionally licensed (such as Canvas or Google Classroom)?
4. Which tool(s)? If you do not remember the exact name, please enter the type (such as class management system, grading assistant, etc.) and any other information you can recall about the tools.
5. How frequently are such requests accepted at your institute?
6. Do such integrations need to go through any security audits?
7. In case of security or privacy incident(s) arise due to the use/integration of personally acquired applications or devices, who handles them? - Myself, Other employees of my institution, Third party service providers
8. In your opinion or experience, what can be the most troubling security/privacy issue resulting from unlicensed technology use?
9. Are there any proactive measures to prevent such issues at your institute?
10. What proactive security and privacy measures does your institute have?
11. What are the primary barriers to having proactive measures?

12. Are you aware of any security or data privacy incident caused by the use of applications or devices not procured by the school? Please explain the incident(s) and how they were handled.
13. Does your institutional policy have any clear recommendation for integrating non-institutionally acquired tools with institutional tools? 1) Clearly allowed for any tools, 2) Clearly denied for all tools, 3) Unsure, and 4) Need to review on a case-by-case basis
14. What are the ways instructors (can) learn about the institutional policies? - 1) Online resources, 2) They are sent over email, 3) Other (please explain)
15. Does your institutional policy have any clear recommendation for actions such as downloading student data by instructors on personally owned devices? YES/NO, explain
16. Please explain When was the last time the institutional policy regarding technology use and data security/privacy was updated?

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS:

17. Please select your gender.
18. Please select your age group.
19. Please enter your job title. This is the final question, so enter "I am done" at the end of your response.
20. Please select the type of the institute you work at.